

Locating service centers optimizing customers' perspective criteria

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Abstract

A network of several demand nodes is considered. We want to locate a number of multiserver facilities at some nodes assuming at least one server must be located at each node. Accordingly, the number of servers has to be more than the nodes number. We propose a model for locating these facilities from customers' perspective in such a way as to minimize the total average queue length, when customers choose the facilities they patronize, by the travel distance (or time) to the facility and the number of servers at the facility. This means that each customer can obtain the service or goods from several (i.e., rather than only one) facilities, according to a probabilistic distribution. Genetic and simulated annealing (SA) algorithms based heuristics are proposed to solve this problem, which belongs to nonlinear integer programming problems. We evaluate the proposed algorithms for the solution quality solving a number of numerical problems. The results indicate that SA whose objective function is around 26% less than that of genetic is of higher performance.

Keywords: Location problem, Queue, Server, Network, Congestion.